

Gene-Based Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Prodrugs and Considerations Regarding Genetically Modified Organisms

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ABSTRACT

During the COVID-19 pandemic caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), novel gene-based anti-SARS-CoV-2 prodrugs (ASPs) were used. ASPs introduce foreign, genetically modified material (e.g., modified mRNA, mod-mRNA) into human cells to induce them to produce a foreign SARS-CoV-2-like spike protein (SP), which is intended to trigger an immune response against SARS-CoV-2. This process meets aspects of the biological definition of a genetically modified organism (GMO). It has been shown that mod-mRNA-based ASPs can be converted into DNA by reverse transcriptase. Plasmid DNA contamination has also been found in mod-mRNA-based ASPs. Both aspects open up the theoretical possibility that genetic material from ASPs could enter the human cell nucleus and be incorporated into the human genome – another GMO criterion. Furthermore, it has been shown that biological effects of gene-based ASPs can be passed on to offspring (probably epigenetically) – another GMO criterion. Even if ethical and legal considerations currently rule out the classification of humans as GMOs, the biological consideration raises complex questions that necessitate a comprehensive and critical scientific and societal debate about such gene-based technologies.

KEYWORDS: SARS-CoV-2; COVID-19 pandemic; gene-based anti-SARS-CoV-2 prodrugs; COVID-19 vaccines; genetically modified organisms

1. Vaccines and Gene-Based Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Prodrugs

Vaccines have been used since the late 18th century, with development in the laboratory beginning in the late 19th century and continuing on an immunological basis in the 20th century (D'Amelio et al. 2016; Plotkin 2014). Although corresponding concepts have been considered since ancient times (Hussein et al. 2015), the widespread use of vaccines was achieved by the English physician Edward Anthony Jenner (1749-1823) in the 1790s with the first vaccine against smallpox (Plotkin 2003; Sern and Markel 2005). During the pandemic with the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) and the associated Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) (Li et al. 2021; Mistry et al. 2022; Rehman et al. 2020; Tang et al. 2020; Theoharides and Kempuraj 2023), the issue of vaccines received broad medical, political and social attention and relevance worldwide (Bhagat et al. 2020). In particular, gene-based products came into focus (Corbett et al. 2020), and it was only through this COVID-19 pandemic that their broad global clinical application and establishment was achieved (Mulligan et al. 2020; Rijkers et al. 2021). Previously, mRNA / DNA-based technologies were mainly the subject of experimental scientific research, especially in cancer (Maruggi et al. 2019; Pardi et al. 2018; Schlake et al. 2012). Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, mRNA products with the aim of immunizing against a respiratory infectious disease had never been approved for public use (Banoun 2023; Dolgin 2021). Viral vector DNA products had also only been used to a limited extent against Ebola, dengue fever and Japanese encephalitis (McCann et al. 2022).

The development of such gene-based products involved technical processes that had been available for a long time (Acevedo-Whitehouse and Bruno 2023; Malone et al. 1989; Sahin et al. 2014), but had never been used on a large or even global scale for human use (Acevedo-Whitehouse and Bruno 2023; Bellavite et al. 2023). mRNA technology was primarily intended to replace or deliver a therapeutic protein (Pardi et al. 2015; Sahin et al. 2014). To combat SARS-CoV-2 novel gene-based products were used whose genetic material encodes the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein (SP) (Jackson et al. 2021), with the aim of triggering an immune response (Bellavite et al. 2023; Kämmerer et al. 2024; Walsh et al. 2020). These gene-based products contained genetically engineered mRNA (e.g. Moderna's Spikevax mRNA-1273 or Pfizer-BioNTech's Comirnaty BNT162b2) or (adenovirus vector-based) DNA (e.g. AstraZeneca's Vaxzevria ChAdOx1 or Johnson & Johnson–Janssen's Ad26.COV2.S) (Barouch 2022). The gene-based mRNA products of Pfizer-BioNTech (Comirnaty BNT162b2) (Oliver et al. 2020) and Moderna

(Spikevax mRNA-1273) (*Oliver et al. 2021*) were among the first substances to be approved (for emergency use) in December 2020 and are currently the most widely used substances in the US and Europe (*Bellavite et al. 2023*). Both products use a lipid nanoparticle (LNP) platform to deliver the nucleoside-modified mRNA (mod-mRNA, m-mRNA) information for the full-length of SARS-CoV-2 SP to instruct the synthesis of virus-like SP in the infiltrated / transfected host cell to elicit virus-neutralizing antibodies (*Aldén et al. 2022; Kämmerer et al. 2024; Walsh et al. 2020*).

The novel gene-based anti-SARS-CoV-2 prodrugs (ASPs) used worldwide do not work like conventional protein-based vaccines or inactivated viral components in the proclaimed activation of the protective immune system (*Banoun 2023*). This is because they deliver their immunization message in the form of foreign modified mRNA / DNA directly into various transfected human host cell types in multiple organ systems, which are then supposed to produce a foreign virus-like SP themselves in order to present it on their surface membrane to secondarily activate the immune system (*Bellavite et al. 2023; Kämmerer et al. 2024; Trougakos et al. 2022*). The body's own, non-immune cells thus become antigen-presenting cells that express a foreign antigen (*Beck et al., 2023; Parry et al. 2023*). In this way, human host cells, pharmacologically transfected by gene-based ASPs, produce foreign SP and / or its subunits / peptide fragments (*Beck et al., 2023; Trougakos et al. 2022*) and release them into the bloodstream (*Cosentino and Marino 2022; Heinz and Stiasny 2021; Jackson et al. 2021*), which can then spread throughout the body (*Trougakos et al. 2022*).

These gene-based ASPs represent a new approach to immunization in which, instead of an inactivated substance (or a subunit thereof), one or more genes encoding proteins of the pathogen are delivered (*Srivastava and Liu 2003*). Such gene-based ASPs have been shown to induce neurogenetic responses (*Trougakos et al. 2022*), including epigenetic reprogramming of, for example, monocyte populations (*Arunachalam et al. 2021*). ASPs, especially of the mRNA and DNA type, have been designed to induce a robust and sustained immune response (*Li et al. 2022a*). For this purpose, these ASPs have been genetically stabilised (e.g. by poly(A) tail (*Kyriakopoulos and McCullough 2021; Sahin et al. 2014*) and 3' untranslated region (3'UTR) of human globin (*Orlandini von Niessen et al. 2019*)) in such a way that the transfected human non-immun host cell is able to produce foreign SP over a longer period of time (*Bellavite et al. 2023; McKernan et al. 2021*), which are more stably incorporated into the host cell plasma membrane

and thus presented by a further genetic modification (leader sequence for translation) (*Bellavite et al. 2023*). Unlike natural mRNA, mod-mRNA from ASPs can remain intact for weeks, allowing long-term expression of SP (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*). As long as such mod-mRNA remains in the transfected human cells, the intracellular production of foreign proteins continues (*Parry et al. 2023*).

In order to stabilise a foreign laboratory mod-mRNA (natural mRNA is highly unstable (*Yang et al. 2003*); average half-life in mammals about 7 h (*Sharova et al. 2008*)) and thus improve its translation in the living organism, genetically modified pseudouridine or methylpseudouridine has been incorporated into ASPs instead of the natural native uridine (*Kämmerer et al. 2024; Morais et al. 2021; Mulrone et al. 2024; Nance and Meier 2021; Park et al. 2021; Yamamoto et al. 2011*). One of the purposes of this is to prevent the natural immune defence against foreign material by toll like receptors (TLRs) and interferons (*Andries et al. 2015; Karikó et al. 2005; Kim et al. 2022; Theoharides and Kempuraj 2023*). It has been shown that N1-methylpseudouridine from ASPs (for their long-lasting product effect (*Karikó et al. 2008*)) can induce ribosomal frameshifts of unknown magnitude during translation, leading to abnormal protein products that can trigger cellular dysfunctions, which in turn can induce neurodegenerative processes (*Parr et al. 2020; Mulrone et al. 2024; Posa 2025*). Corresponding studies on the effects of these frameshift products, especially on autoimmune, carcinogenic, neuroinflammation and neurodegenerative processes in the human body, are not yet available (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*).

In addition, LNP (diameter about 100 nm (*Buschmann et al. 2021*)) have been added to ASPs as a protective cover (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*) for foreign RNA (Pfizer-BioNTech's Comirnaty BNT162b2; Moderna's Spikevax mRNA-1273), foreign DNA (AstraZeneca's Vaxzevria ChAdOx119; Johnson & Johnson–Janssen's Ad26.COV2.S) or foreign protein (Novavax's Nuvaxovid NVX-CoV2373) structures, as these would otherwise be recognised as foreign by the human immune system and broken down (*Karikó et al. 2005; De Beuckelaer et al. 2016*). The incorporated mod-mRNA was detectable in the human body for weeks due to the protective LNP (*Castruita et al. 2023; Fertig et al. 2020; Röltgen et al. 2022*). The synthetically produced ionizable lipids of the LNP are estimated to have a half-life of 20 to 30 days in vivo (*Comirnaty 2021*). LNP are used to transport mRNA and enhance cell wall penetration, which is already used in chemotherapeutics for the treatment of brain tumours (*Anand et al. 2019*) and other pharmaceutical products (*Gómez-Aguado et al. 2020; Hou et al. 2021*). LNP have been shown to easily

penetrate biological tissues and membranes and thus reach all organs (*Di et al. 2022; Igyártó and Qin 2024; Parry et al. 2023*). LNP have also been shown to be able to cross the blood-brain barrier and the blood-placental barrier (*Ndeupen et al. 2021; Swingle et al. 2023; Turni and Lefringhausen 2022; Wick et al. 2010; Zhou et al. 2018*). LNPs can reach placental cells such as trophoblasts, which is being discussed for the treatment of placental diseases during pregnancy (*Swingle et al. 2023*). Another aspect is the use of LNPs for gene delivery to fetal organs (*Abostait et al. 2024*). It could be shown that LNPs can effectively deliver mRNA for gene editing enzymes to the fetal mouse brain, resulting in successful transfection and editing of brain cells (*Gao et al. 2024*). Currently, such ASP effects on humans are unknown (*Zhong et al. 2024*). In a recent study, mRNA-based ASP (Moderna's Spikevax mRNA-1273) intramuscularly given to pregnant mice rapidly circulated in maternal blood and crossed the placenta within 1 h to spread in the fetal circulation. Although spike mRNA could accumulate in fetal tissues, mainly the liver and get translated into SP (*Chen et al. 2025*). There is currently no final assessment of the human health consequences of this LNP (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*).

Furthermore, plasmid DNA contamination (legally correct: undeclared admixtures from the manufacturing process) was detected in the bivalent mRNA products from both Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna and that exceeded the limits set by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) (*Banoun 2023; Buckhaults 2023; Kämmerer et al. 2024; König and Kirchner 2024; McKernan 2023; McKernan et al. 2023; Pekova 2025; Raoult 2024; Speicher et al. 2023, 2025; Wang et al. 2024a*). The impact of such plasmid DNA contaminations on human health is not yet known (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*). However, it has been known for years that plasmid DNA can integrate into the genome, with the risk of insertional mutagenesis (*Sahin et al. 2014*). Further genetic analyses proved, worryingly, that residual plasmid DNA represents not only fragments of the DNA matrices encoding for SP gene, but all genes from the plasmid, including the simian virus 40 (SV40) promoter/enhancer and the antibiotic resistance gene (to Kanamycin) (*Kämmerer et al. 2024; Raoult 2024*). This is a concern because SV40 is associated with cancer in humans (*Carbone et al. 2020; Kolevtykh 2024; Rotondo et al. 2019*). SV40 is a DNA tumor virus originally found as a contaminant in polio vaccines administered between 1955 and 1963 (*Poulin and DeCaprio 2006*). Double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) has also been detected (*Banoun 2023; Igyártó and Qin 2024*) in the mRNA products from Pfizer-BioNTech (*Comirnaty 2021*) and Moderna (*Moderna 2021*). This dsRNA can activate innate immune sensors, trigger inflammatory responses and restrict protein translation from mRNA (*Karikó et*

al. 2005; 2008; 2011) and is supported in current animal studies with corresponding ASP from Pfizer-BioNTech (*Li et al. 2022a*). The impact of such dsRNA contaminations on human health is not yet known (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*). These plasmid DNA and dsRNA contaminations exceeded the regulatory limits and varied between the different ASP batches (indicative of deviations in purity and heterogeneity) (*Banoun 2023; Schmeling et al. 2023*).

Due to these novel mechanisms, especially at the gene level (*Polykretis and McCullough 2022*), it is controversial whether these genetically engineered pharmaceuticals even meet the definition of “vaccines” or should rather be considered “immunostimulatory gene-based prodrugs” (*Bellavite et al. 2023; Cosentino and Marino 2022*). Prodrugs are initially pharmacologically inactive substances that are converted into a pharmacologically active product in the body. There has been and continues to be a complex medical, scientific, regulatory, and legal debate regarding the respective classifications of “vaccine”, “pro-vaccine”, “genetically engineered vaccines”, “prodrug” and “gene therapy product” (*Banoun 2023*). According to the European and French pharmacopoeias, mRNA products should not be considered as vaccines and the principle of action of mRNA-based ASP corresponds to the definition of gene therapy products (*Banoun 2023*). Moderna stated in 2020 that “mRNA is currently considered by the FDA as a gene therapy product” (*Moderna 2020*). BioNTech also referred to mRNA products as gene therapy products (*Sahin et al. 2014*). Gene therapy products are nucleic acids designed to induce target cells to produce an antigen that induces the production of antibodies. According to the FDA, “gene therapy is a medical intervention based on the modification of the genetic material of living cells” (*Murphy 1998*). Banoun (2023) describes the complexity of this terminology and classification dilemma in detail (*Banoun 2023*).

2. Genetically Modified Organisms and Legal Aspects

Genetically modified organisms (GMOs) are organisms with modified genetic material / properties (*Cacciabaudo et al. 2014*) that have been created using genetic engineering techniques (*Lamont and Lacey 2020*) and do not occur naturally by mating or natural recombination (*Garcia 2001; European Union Directive 2001/18/EC; Fernández Albújar and van der Meulen 2017; Trkulja et al. 2018*). In this process, genetic material (e.g. specific DNA segments) are isolated and transferred from one organism into another (*Del Val et al. 2010*), which affects genes from the same

species (intragenic) or from different species (transgenic) (Lamont and Lacey 2020). GMOs therefore carry foreign genetic material that is stably integrated into their original genome and passed on to their offspring through inheritance (Trkulja et al. 2018). The difference to traditional hybridization is that unnatural genetic manipulation through genetic engineering techniques is an imposed hybridization that can even cross the species boundary (Garcia 2001). The aim of genetic engineering is to create modified organisms with new and advantageous properties and characteristics (Khan et al. 2016; Laforest and Nadakuduti 2022; Trkulja et al. 2018). GMOs can, for example, express additional proteins through these genetic engineering techniques (Manzanares-Palenzuela et al. 2014), e.g. insulin (for treatment of diabetes), interferon (for viral diseases), coagulation factors (for treatment of haemophilia), etc. (Trkulja et al. 2018).

In 1980, scientists were able to insert genes from one organism into the DNA chain of another for the first time. The first transgenic cultures followed in the United States (US) in 1987 (Garcia 2001). The first GMO to be officially approved in the US by FDA on 18 May 1994 was *Flavr Savr*® (Calgene, Inc., Davis, California, USA), a tomato hybrid designed to last longer (Trkulja et al. 2018). Genetically modified food products have been available to consumers since 1996 (Trkulja et al. 2018). Many crops, such as maize, soya, tomato, potato and cotton, have been modified to be more resistant to pests, herbicides, diseases (insects, fungus, bacteria, viruses) or environmental factors or better able to cope with drought, soil salinity, and stress (Abbas et al. 2024). Bacteria and yeasts are also genetically modified to produce certain substances such as insulin for the treatment of diabetes or enzymes for the food industry. In some cases, animals have been genetically modified to increase their growth rate or promote certain traits such as disease resistance. Technical intervention at the genetic level therefore affects plants, microorganisms and animals (Coelho and García Díez 2015; Garcia 2001; Trkulja et al. 2018; Yali 2022).

There is much debate about the pros and cons of GMOs, particularly in relation to environmental, health risks as well as ethical and social issues (Cao et al. 2023; Wilson 2007). Supporters argue that GMOs can help solve global challenges such as hunger (more productive, cheaper and more resilient foods) and climate challenges (temperature resistance) (Abbas et al. 2024; Li et al. 2022b; Rasheed et al. 2022; Singh et al. 2022), while critics express concerns about possible long-term risks to human health, ecosystems, environment and biodiversity (gene transfer / flow / hybridization) (Abbas et al. 2024; Campbell et al. 2019; Coelho and García Díez 2015; Neira-

Monsalve et al. 2023; Singh et al. 2022). The safety profile and level of risk of such genetic engineering techniques depends on the technical process used, the genetic properties and the final application, and cannot be generalized to all GMO processes. The assessment and evaluation must be carried out individually for each GMO measure.

A patent is a right granted by the state to the inventor to make, sell or supply his new, useful and nonobvious invention to the exclusion of all others for a limited period of time (Article 3(1) BioPatent Directive (BioPatRL); Article 52(1) European Patent Convention (EPC); Article 1(1) Patent Law (PatG); Article 27(1) first sentence TRIPS Agreement) (*Dederer 2024; Hickey and Ward 2024; Shadlen et al. 2020*). During this period, the inventor is entitled to exclude all others from commercially exploiting his invention. This monopoly is granted to the inventor as a financial incentive to encourage innovation and research. The possibility of patent protection is crucial for companies to invest in costly and risky research and development. A patentee can grant a licence to others to practice the invention, allowing them to make, use, sell or import the invention, usually in exchange for consideration (e.g. licence fees) (*Hickey and Ward 2024; Shadlen et al. 2020*).

Patents are particularly important in the pharmaceutical sector. Research and development costs, as well as scientific and economic uncertainties, are very high (most research does not lead to marketable products). Approval of new products requires complex clinical trials, and there are significant delays between invention and market launch. In contrast, pharmaceuticals, once developed, are comparatively easy to copy. Patents are intended to counteract this. For a long time, pharmaceutical patents were the exception rather than the rule. While pharmaceutical patents had long been available in the US (1960s), this was not the case in other wealthy countries. In Europe, for example, only the United Kingdom, France and West Germany allowed pharmaceutical patents until 1970. From the mid-1970s to the early 1990s, pharmaceutical patents became the norm throughout the Global North: Belgium, the Netherlands, Italy, Sweden, Switzerland, Japan in the late 1970s; Canada, Denmark, Austria in the 1980s; Australia, Greece, Ireland, New Zealand, Norway, Portugal, Spain in the early 1990s. Finland, which allowed pharmaceutical patents in 1995, was the last western european country to do so (*Chatterjee 2013; Liu and La Croix 2015; Qian 2007; Shadlen et al. 2020*). In the Global South, the introduction of pharmaceutical patents was delayed, primarily due to financial concerns.

Through the lobbying of transnational pharmaceutical organizations and the TRIPS Agreement (since 1995) (TRIPS: Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights), almost all countries in the world followed suit by the 2000s (*Liu and La Croix 2015; Shadlen et al. 2020*).

GMOs can also be patented and most GMOs are protected by patents (*Dederer 2024; Iwasaka 2000; O'Connor 1993; Nawaz et al. 2020; Straus 2000*), also genetically modified subjects, such as animals (*Dresser 1988; Kambic 1988; Seltzer 1988*). The intersection of patent law and GMOs presents a complex, contentious and evolving legal landscape in the realm of intellectual property law. The GMO patenting involves navigating a complex interplay of legal, ethical, scientific, economic and regulatory challenges. The legal framework involves a combination of biotechnology regulations and intellectual property protections, with patents playing a significant role in protecting GMO developers (*Roorda 2017; Smith and Kong 2022*). Biotech industries often seek dual protection for their inventions through patents and contractual structures, aiming to monopolize the application and pricing of their inventions. The potential for monopolistic control by a few corporations is a significant concern (*Abbas et al. 2024; Xu et al. 2022*). The debate around patenting human genetic material involves balancing innovation incentives with moral, societal and political implications. Isolated human genes cannot be patented, but their use in molecular biology has led to controversial discussion (*Caulfield et al. 2000; Sherkow and Greely 2015*). In Germany, "the human body in the individual phases of its formation and development, including the germ cells, as well as the mere discovery of one of its components, including the sequence or partial sequence of a gene, cannot be patentable inventions" (Paragraph 1a (1) Patent Act) (*Federal Ministry of Justice 2025*).

In legal terms, GMOs are usually owned by the companies who hold the rights to the underlying patents, breeding technologies or genetic modifications. This means that the companies that develop GMOs often also have control over the use and sale of these organisms. A patent gives the owner the exclusive right to use the technology for a certain period of time and to exclude others from using it. If other users want to use these GMOs, they have to pay licence fees. These licence fees can be a major problem, in particular for small farmers and actors with less financial resources, and can put a lot of economic pressure on them (*Mariappan and Zhou 2019*). In the medical field, licence fees and drug prices can become unaffordable, especially for poorer countries. The right to intellectual property then clashes with the indi-

vidual's right to health (*Khachigian 2020*). In many cases, GMOs are governed by licence agreements that allow licensees to use the GMOs under certain conditions. The legal protection of GMOs can cause major and existential problems for non-GMO users (non-licensees) with patent infringements if their products (e.g. crops) are inadvertently contaminated with GMO components (*Beretich 2014*).

At the international level, there is no uniform GMO legislation. Different countries have different GMO regulations. For example, labelling of genetically modified human foods is not mandatory in the USA, Argentina, Canada, Uruguay, Mexico, Chile, Paraguay and Egypt. In the European Union (EU), products containing >0.9% of GMOs and in Brazil and Australia, products containing >1% of GMOs must be labelled. The threshold for GMO labelling in Japan is 5% (*Trkulja et al. 2018*). US legislation is based on the assumption that biotechnology as a process in itself does not pose any unique or special risks, so that foods produced this way must be subject to the same rules as conventionally produced foods (*Landrum et al. 2019; Evanega et al. 2022*). EU legislation, on the other hand, assumes that foods produced from genetically modified plants may pose new risks that need to be assessed and specifically regulated (*Trkulja et al. 2018*). The same international differences exist in the patenting of genes, with different countries taking different positions on the admissibility of patent claims on genetic material (*Nicol et al. 2019*). The EU and the US have different approaches to the regulation and patenting of GMOs (*Roorda 2017; Zimny 2015*). This further complicates the issue in an international context.

EU research into the safety of genetically modified crops and foods was initiated in 1986 (*Garcia 2001*). Various pieces of legislation have followed to regulate the use of GMOs: directives 90/220/EC, 97/258/EC, 2001/18/EC on genetically modified foods; directives 90/219/EEC, 94/51/EC, 98/81/EC on the contained use of GMOs; directives 90/220/EEC, 94/15/EC, 97/35/EC, 2001/18/EC on the experimental release and placing on the market of GMOs; et cetera (*Garcia 2001*). The patenting of genetically modified plants, for example, is governed in the EU by biopatent law, which is embedded in general patent law (EC Biopatent Directive 98/44/EC; BioPatRL) (*Dederer 2024*). This harmonized biopatent law across Europe (*Dederer 2024*). The main objective of EU legislation on GMOs was to establish an EU-wide safety assessment and authorisation procedure (*Garcia 2001*) to protect human health and the environment and to ensure the free movement of GMO products within the EU (*Jiang 2020; Trkulja et al. 2018*). All

regulations create requirement which must be met by any company or scientific research institution before the development, use or placement of GMOs. The EU's Biotech Directive attempts to balance patentability and market freedom, but challenges remain in ensuring freedom to operate in secondary markets (*Godt 2018*). At this point, the aspects of process patents and product patents in the EU Biopatent Directive 98/44/EC (BioPatRL) should be mentioned (*Dederer 2024; Directive 98/44/EC 1998*). Furthermore, it should be noted that there are differences between GMO law (right of permission to use) and patent law (right of exclusion of use). For example, intellectual property rights, namely the patent law, can block access to and use of GMOs in the area of GMO law, and this in a complex, partly legally unclear, partly interlocking manner (*Dederer 2024*). In addition, moral issues in biotechnology patents remain a contentious issue, with the European Patent Office playing a key role in addressing these concerns (*Crespi 2000*).

The paramount importance of an appropriate and secure legal framework for genetic engineering research, innovation and development is undisputed. Patents are crucial for investment, progress, and innovation in research and development, including the development of genetically modified foods and animals in the field of biotechnology. The economic and financial impact of patents can extend beyond inventive innovation, as patents also influence market dynamics and access to resources, raising ethical and moral concerns. The patenting of GMOs continues to face complex challenges. The ongoing controversial debate highlights the need for a balanced approach that considers both the benefits and drawbacks of the innovation, as well as the ethical implications of patenting life forms. Although the patenting of genetically modified life forms is legally possible, it remains a complex and controversial issue with significant ethical, economic, financial and legal dimensions that require careful consideration and continuous dialogue among stakeholders.

3. Genetic Effects of SARS-CoV-2 and Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Prodrugs on the Organism

The SP of SARS-CoV-2 can penetrate into the cell nucleus and cause dysregulation at the level of gene expression (*Kim et al. 2021*). The localisation of SARS-CoV-2 SP in the cell nucleus was reported as early as 2020 (*Zhang et al. 2020*) prior to the global market launch of products (*Oliver et al. 2020; 2021*) genetically designed to induce the human body cells to produce non-

human virus-like SP itself. Further studies followed, with the detection of nuclear localization signals (NLS) in SARS-CoV-2 SP ([Sattar et al. 2023](#)), which is new and unique in the group of SARS coronaviruses ([Igyártó and Qin 2024](#)). This NLS enables the viral SP to be transported to the cell nucleus. In addition, viral spike mRNA may also reach the cell nucleus together with SP ([Sattar et al. 2023](#)). However, it is not yet fully understood how often and under what conditions this occurs, nor what biological, physiological or pathological relevance this may have. The nucleocapsid protein of SARS-CoV-2 also possesses NLS, with effects on host cell functions ([Wang et al. 2024b](#)). Other SARS-CoV-2 proteins (e.g., NSP1, NSP5, NSP9, NSP13) also exhibit nuclear localizations in the cell ([Zhang et al. 2020](#)). It is currently still unclear to what biologically relevant extent this nuclear localization occurs.

It has long been known that non-retroviral virus-RNA can persist in DNA form ([Klenerman et al. 1997](#)) and can integrate into human and other mammalian host cells ([Horie et al. 2010](#); [Acevedo-Whitehouse and Bruno 2023](#)). Regarding the SARS-CoV-2 virus, it has already been shown that SARS-CoV-2 RNA can be reverse-transcribed (via endogenous LINE-1 retrotransposons) and integrated into the genome of the infected cell and be expressed as chimeric transcripts fusing viral with cellular sequences ([Zhang et al. 2021](#)). Importantly, such chimeric transcripts are detected in patient-derived tissues ([Zhang et al. 2021](#)). However, subgenomic fragments were integrated, not the complete viral genome. Production of infectious viruses from these integrants is not possible ([Zhang et al. 2021](#)). Acevedo-Whitehouse and Bruno (2023) describe in detail the function of LINE-1 and its cis and trans effects ([Acevedo-Whitehouse and Bruno 2023](#)). LINE-1 retrotransposons are elements of the human genome capable of reverse transcription and integration ([Hancks and Kazazian 2012](#)). It has already been shown that, after reverse transcription, DNA copies (cDNA) of SARS-CoV-2 RNA sequences can be integrated into the genome of infected human cells ([Zhang et al. 2021](#)). A further study has suggested that the interaction between coronavirus sequences and endogenous retrotransposon could be a potential viral integration mechanism ([Yin et al. 2021](#)). These points of reverse transcription and genomic integration were confirmed in further studies ([Zhang et al. 2023](#)). This could potentially explain the prolonged detection of viral RNA in patients after COVID-19 recovery. However, it must be mentioned at this point that this aspect is still being critically discussed ([Grandi et al. 2021](#); [Parry et al., 2021](#); [Smits et al. 2021](#)). AL-Eitan and Mihyar provide a detailed insight into this scientific conflict ([AL-Eitan and Mihyar 2024](#)). Research into the transcription of SARS-CoV-2 RNA into DNA and its transcription into the human genome is highly topical.

Further research is needed to clarify these points and understand the implications for long-term viral RNA presence in recovered patients.

To combat SARS-CoV-2, novel gene-based products have been used that contain biotechnologically produced genetic information encoding for the SARS-CoV-2 SP. The human body cells transfected by ASP are intended to synthesize virus-like SP and present it to the immune system in order to stimulate the production of virus-neutralizing antibodies and thus an immune response (*Aldén et al. 2022; Kämmerer et al. 2024; Walsh et al. 2020*). How precisely ASPs train innate immune cells to shape protective host defense mechanisms remains unknown (*Simonis et al. 2025*). Gene-based ASPs are genetically modified and stabilized (*Bellavite et al. 2023; Igyártó and Qin 2024; Kyriakopoulos and McCullough 2021; Morais et al. 2021; Mulronev et al. 2024; Orlandini von Niessen et al. 2019; Parr et al. 2020*) and have an impact at gene level (*Arunachalam et al. 2021; Bellavite et al. 2023; Cosentino and Marino 2022; Trougakos et al. 2022*). Through such biotechnological modifications, ASP components can penetrate and cross biological tissues and membranes (*Di et al. 2022; Igyártó and Qin 2024; Parry et al. 2023*), the blood-brain barrier and the blood-placental barrier (*Abostait et al. 2024; Chen et al. 2025; Gao et al. 2024; Ndeupen et al. 2021; Swingle et al. 2023; Turni and Lefringhausen 2022; Wick et al. 2010; Zhou et al. 2018*).

In a recent study, mRNA-based ASP (Moderna's Spikevax mRNA-1273) intramuscularly given to pregnant mice rapidly circulated in maternal blood and crossed the placenta within 1 h to spread in the fetal circulation. Although spike mRNA could accumulate in fetal tissues, mainly the liver and be translated into SP and trigger a corresponding immune response (*Chen et al. 2025*). Previous animal studies have shown that mRNA-LNP products cause growth disorders in fetuses (*Chaudhary et al. 2024*) and that LNP is detected in fetal tissue (*Abostait et al. 2024; Zietsman et al. 2024*). According to the best current knowledge (September 2025), no data are available for human fetuses. Previous human studies have only looked for ASP components in non-fetal tissue (e.g. placenta), days after ASP injection (*Prahl et al. 2022, Santos et al. 2022*). How much, for how long, where and with what health consequences injection components are produced (e.g. SP) and circulate (e.g. LNP) in the human body after the application of gene-based ASPs in particular has not yet been conclusively clarified (*Bansal et al. 2021; Bellavite et al. 2023; Brogna et al. 2023; Castruita et al. 2023; Cognetti and Miller 2021; Fertig et al. 2020; Ogata et al. 2022; Parry et al. 2023; Röltgen et al. 2022; Trougakos et al. 2022*), because the systemic biodistribution and disposition of ASPs (of mRNA and DNA codes) (*Parry et al. 2023*) has not

yet been investigated to the necessary extent (*Banoun 2023; Cosentino and Marino 2022*). There is only limited knowledge on how SP, LNP, various modifications of mRNA and other ASP components as well as their contamination (plasmid DNA, dsRNA) in the human body, since no specific studies, especially no long-term studies, have been conducted on this topic (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*).

The SP is detectable in plasma from individuals as early as 1 day after the first ASP incorporation (from the mRNA products of Pfizer-BioNTech's Comirnaty BNT162b2 and Moderna's Spikevax mRNA-1273 (*Ogata et al. 2022*)) and for at least another 60 days in human lymph node biopsy studies (*Röltgen et al. 2022; Yonker et al. 2023*). In addition, spike protein from ASP injection has been detected in circulating exosomes for at least four months (*Bansal et al. 2021*). A recent study detected SP in plasma for over 700 days (*Bhattacharjee et al. 2025*). Contrary to the initial official statements, the SP production by human body cells is not limited to the intramuscular injection site and does not end within a few days (*Kämmerer et al. 2024*). Even mRNA components of ASPs have been detected in the human body (lymph nodes, plasma and other organ tissues) for days (15d (*Fertig et al. 2020*), 30d (*Krauson et al. 2023*)). This is remarkable because natural mRNA is highly unstable (*Yang et al. 2003*), with an average half-life in mammals of about 7 h (*Sharova et al. 2008*). Thus, the statement made, especially at the beginning of ASP market launch, that corresponding products would be degraded in vivo within hours or a few days is also no longer tenable (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*).

It has been shown that SARS-CoV-2 RNA can enter the cell nucleus and can be reverse-transcribed into DNA and integrated into the genome of infected human cells (*Zhang et al. 2021; 2023*). With regard to ASPs, a comparable transport of the spike protein and / or mRNA of ASPs into the cell nucleus is theoretically also possible (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*), but has not yet been scientifically proven nor excluded for mRNA products (*Acevedo-Whitehouse and Bruno 2023*). However, this risk of genomic integration can occur with plasmid DNA-based products (*Wang et al. 2024a*) and vectorized products (*Harui et al. 1999; Zheng et al. 2000*), which has been known for years. Regarding mRNA-based ASPs, the paradigm has been that mRNA cannot be converted into DNA and thus cannot integrate into the human genome. It has already been shown in the immortalized human hepatocyte cell line Huh7 that reverse transcription of artificially produced mod-mRNA from Pfizer-BioNTech's ASP into a DNA copy (cDNA) is also possible (*Aldén et al. 2022*). This was already known in preclinical animal studies on liver cells

with Pfizer-BioNTech's ASP Comirnaty BNT162b2 (Aldén *et al.* 2022). Uptake of BNT162b2 into human liver cells resulted in changes in LINE-1 expression and distribution. Furthermore, it has been shown that BNT162b2 mRNA is reverse retranscribed intracellularly into cDNA as early as 6 h after BNT162b2 exposure (Aldén *et al.* 2022). A possible mechanism for reverse transcription is through endogenous reverse transcriptase LINE-1, and the nucleus protein distribution of LINE-1 is elevated by BNT162b2 (Aldén *et al.* 2022). Based on these data, concerns have been raised that BNT162b2-derived cDNA may be integrated into the host genome, which may compromise the integrity of the human genome and potentially lead to genotoxic side effects (Aldén *et al.* 2022). At present, this point has not yet been conclusively clarified. According to current knowledge (September 2025), there are no further studies in this regard, especially regarding the transferability of findings from cell lines to human cells and tissue *in vivo*. Therefore, further studies are urgently needed to definitively clarify the impact of such ASPs on human genomic integrity. This includes whole-genome sequencing of human cells exposed to such ASPs. However, these data suggest the theoretical possibility of intergenerational transmission when germ cells incorporate these ASP cDNA into the host genome (Parry *et al.* 2023). In this context, it should be noted that mRNA from the products Pfizer-BioNTech (Comirnaty BNT162b2) (Comirnaty 2021) and Moderna (Spikevax mRNA-1273) (Moderna 2021) have been detected in both the testes and the ovaries, among many other organs and tissues (EMA 2021). Whether this occurs *in vivo* remains to be determined (Merchant 2022).

The theoretical possibility, but not yet practically proven, of retropositioning the genetic material from ASPs suggests that the production of a foreign non-human protein (namely the viral SP) may occur throughout life or even across generations (Domazet-Lošo 2022). Studies in mice have already shown that even a single exposure to mRNA-LNP complexes can inhibit adaptive immune responses and alter innate immune fitness in a heritable manner (Qin *et al.* 2022). Further studies in mice demonstrate the transmission of either trained immunity or tolerance across generations (Katzmarski *et al.* 2021), in the sense of transgenerational inheritance of immune traits. The mechanism of this inheritance remains to be elucidated (Simonis *et al.* 2025). It is likely to be mediated in part by DNA methylation changes that may have induced inflammatory messengers (interferons, cytokines) (Katzmarski *et al.* 2021; Qin *et al.* 2022). A recent study showed that mRNA-based ASP injection (BNT162b2 and mRNA-1273) in humans significantly establishes histone H3 lysine 27 acetylation (H3K27ac) at promoters of human

monocyte-derived macrophages, suggesting epigenetic memory (*Simonis et al. 2025*). Furthermore, H3K27ac at promoters was enriched for G-quadruplex DNA secondary structure-forming sequences in macrophage-derived nucleosome-depleted regions, linking epigenetic memory to nucleic acid structure (*Simonis et al. 2025*). Thus, mRNA-based ASPs induce extensive and persistent epigenetic marks at promoter regions. These persistent and profound epigenetic marks affect genes that encode cytokines (*Simonis et al. 2025*). ASPs can therefore trigger epigenetic changes in body cells and thus influence gene regulation. This demonstrates the potential of ASPs to penetrate gene regulatory regions in cells. Similar findings were recently made for SARS-CoV-2 infections which trigger long-lasting epigenetic and transcriptional modifications in macrophages, monocytes and hematopoietic stem and progenitor cells (HSPC) (*Cheong et al. 2023; Theobald et al. 2021*). Note, H3K27ac is a critical post-translational modification that regulates chromatin structure and gene expression, which plays a significant role in various cancers (*Zhu et al. 2025*). SARS-CoV-2 causes profound and persistent epigenetic changes in the host, affecting 3D chromatin architecture and histone modifications (*Wang et al. 2023*) as well as long-lasting post-infectious DNA methylation patterns (*Hong et al. 2025*).

Whether such immune inheritance occurs in humans treated with mRNA-based ASPs remains to be clarified urgently. The consideration of inserting new, foreign, non-human genetic material from ASPs into the human genome is a serious problem, especially when it occurs at the level of the reproductive stem cells (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*). At this point, it should also be noted that the biological consequences of the plasmid DNA and dsRNA contamination detected in ASP, especially at the genetic level, are still completely unclear (*Igyártó and Qin 2024*). Biodistribution, cellular uptake, endosomal escape, translation rates, functional half-life, inactivation kinetics, long-term expression, integration into the genome, transmission to the germline, horizontal transmission, passage into sperm, embryo/fetal and perinatal toxicity, genotoxicity and tumorigenicity have not yet been conclusively investigated and clarified for the human organism (*Acevedo-Whitehouse and Bruno 2023; Banoun 2023*).

4. Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Prodrugs in the Context of Genetically Modified Organisms

During the COVID-19 pandemic, novel gene-based ASPs were used for the first time for such an indication and on such a global scale to stimulate transfected human cells to unnaturally produce a foreign SARS-CoV-2-like SP to activate an immune response. This novel gene-based immune stimulation affects millions of people worldwide, including children and adolescents. How ASPs work in detail, how long ASP components persists in the human body, tissue, and cells, and how long ASP effects last, has not yet been conclusively clarified. Currently, it is unknown whether ASP components can penetrate the human cell nucleus, which has already been demonstrated for SARS-CoV-2 components. Regarding mRNA-based ASPs, the paradigm has been that mRNA cannot be converted into DNA and thus cannot integrate into the human genome. Interestingly, it has recently been shown that mRNA of ASPs can be converted into DNA by reverse transcriptase. The resulting theoretical possibility of the integration of foreign genetic material from ASPs into the human genome therefore urgently needs to be further critically debated and scientifically analyzed. Furthermore, contaminants with plasmid DNA and dsRNA has also been found in ASPs, the genetic effects of which on the human genome are not yet fully understood. However, the risk of genomic integration has already been demonstrated for other plasmid DNA products and vectorised products. There is also an urgent need for further clarification and scientific analysis of the inheritance of ASP-related cell/gene effects to offspring. Studies in mice have already shown that the effects of ASP in terms of altered immunity are passed on to offspring and thus across generations. Possibly through altered DNA methylation. The exact biological mechanism of this inheritance and its relevance for humans are still poorly understood and require further research.

Plants, animals or microorganisms can be genetically modified into GMOs with novel properties and characteristics, for example to produce foreign proteins that would never have been produced naturally in their untreated state. This externally-triggered intracellular foreign protein synthesis occurs through the introduction of genetically engineered material into human cells. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) definition states that an organism is considered a GMO “which contains genetic material that has been deliberately altered and which does not occur naturally through breeding or selection” ([EFSA 2025](#)). The cell compartment (nucleus, cytoplasm) of the organism in which this foreign genetic material must be located in order to be considered a GMO is not precisely defined here. The World Health Organization

(WHO) defines GMOs as organisms "in which the genetic material (DNA) has been altered in a way that does not occur naturally by mating and/or natural recombination" ([WHO 2025](#)). With regard to gene-based ASPs, the following points are currently relevant for GMO discourse: 1) the presence of foreign, biotechnologically modified genetic material (e.g., m-mRNA) in human host cells, 2) the resulting unnaturally produced virus-like foreign protein (SP) in human host cells, and 3) evidence of inheritance of new traits to offspring (probably epigenetic based on animal studies). However, points 1 and 2 alone, although they represent partial aspects of the GMO definition, are not sufficient to meet the full definition of GMO. Regarding point 3, it is discussed that only epigenetically modified organisms should not be classified as GMOs ([Faltus 2023](#)). Cell nuclear penetration and genome integration of ASP components, although theoretically conceivable, have not yet been scientifically proven. Only a few non-peer-reviewed preprint reports exist on this highly sensitive issue ([Catanzaro et al. 2025](#); [von Ranke et al. 2025](#)). Therefore, based on current knowledge, the GMO objection cannot be applied from an objective biological point of view to humans with gene-based ASP incorporation.

Interestingly, Article 2 of EU Directive 2001/18/EC explicitly excludes humans from its definition of GMOs. This is remarkable from a biotechnological perspective, because humans, as biologically animals (classified as mammals within the order of primates), can also be genetically modified, for example, using the highly controversial CRISPR-Cas9 techniques ([Jinek et al. 2012](#)). This EU directive does not explicitly require genomic integration or a change in the DNA sequence for GMO classification ([Halford 2019](#)), although in practice it is often clarified that changes in nucleotide sequences must be present ([Faltus 2023](#)). The explicit exclusion of humans is based on social-ethical-legal-regulatory rather than biotechnological-logical reasons. The GMO exclusion is based on the legal definition and not on biotechnological practical and logical possibilities. Even if a genetically modified human being could be classified as a GMO according to objective biological criteria, the law deliberately refuses to adopt this classification. This does not represent a definitional problem, but rather an expression of a normative act: not because humans cannot be GMOs, but because they may not be treated as such for ethical and constitutional reasons. This exclusion is not a scientific inaccuracy, but rather a deliberate deviation from scientific terminology in the service of protecting human dignity. The legal order thus sets a conscious example against any form of biological or technologizing

view of human beings. Categorizing a human being as a GMO would open a logic that fundamentally contradicts the basic idea of human dignity, the equality of all human beings, and their legal inaccessibility. It would not only suggest a shift in perspective from subject to object, but also open the door to regulatory consequences that are incompatible with the human rights order. Therefore, current law excludes humans from the scope of GMO regulation not despite their potential biological classification, but precisely because of the associated ethical implications. This clearly illustrates that the law is not solely committed to biological reality, but rather draws its own normative boundaries on key issues of humanity, in favor of an anthropocentric understanding of person, dignity, and freedom. May this concept of humanity retain its normative power even in the face of future technological, scientific and social challenges and continue to exist as an unshakable guideline in dealing with human existence.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, R., Ullah, Q., Javaid, R., et al., 2024. Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs) in agriculture: a comprehensive review of environmental impacts. Benefits, and concerns. *J. Xi'an Shiyu University*. 20, 583-611.
- Abostait, A., Abdelkarim, M., Bao, Z., et al., 2024. Optimizing lipid nanoparticles for fetal gene delivery in vitro, ex vivo, and aided with machine learning. *J. Control. Release*. 376, 678-700.
- Acevedo-Whitehouse, K., Bruno, R., 2023. Potential health risks of mRNA-based vaccine therapy: A hypothesis. *Med. Hypotheses*. 171, 111015.
- Aldén, M., Olofsson F.F., Yang, D., et al., 2022. Intracellular reverse transcription of Pfizer BioNTech COVID-19 mRNA vaccine BNT162b2 in vitro in human liver cell line. *Curr. Iss. Mol. Biol.* 44, 1115-26.
- AL-Eitan, L., Mihyar, A. 2024. The controversy of SARS-CoV-2 integration into the human genome. *Rev. Med. Virol.* 34(1), e2511.
- Anand, A., Sugumaran, A., Narayanasamy, D., 2019. Brain targeted delivery of anticancer drugs. Prospective approach using solid lipid nanoparticles. *IET Nanobiotechnol.* 13, 353-62.
- Andries, O., Mc Cafferty, S., De Smedt, S.C., et al., 2015. N1-methylpseudouridine-incorporated mRNA outperforms pseudouridine-incorporated mRNA by providing enhanced protein expression and reduced immunogenicity in mammalian cell lines and mice. *J. Control Release*. 217, 337-44.
- Arunachalam, P.S., Scott, M.K., Hagan, T., et al., 2021. Systems vaccinology of the BNT162b2 mRNA vaccine in humans. *Nature*. 596, 410-6.
- Banoun, H., 2023. mRNA: Vaccine or Gene Therapy? The Safety Regulatory Issues. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24, 10514.
- Bansal, S., Perincheri, S., Fleming, T., et al., 2021. Cutting Edge: Circulating Exosomes with COVID Spike Protein Are Induced by BNT162b2 (Pfizer-BioNTech) Vaccination prior to Development of Antibodies: A Novel Mechanism for Immune Activation by mRNA Vaccines. *J. Immunol.* 207, 2405-10.
- Barouch, D.H., 2022. Covid-19 vaccines - immunity, variants, boosters. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 387, 1011-20.
- Beck, A., Diertenberger, H., Kunz, S.N., et al., 2023. Emergence of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein at the vaccination site. *Immun. Inflamm. Dis.* 11(3), e827.
- Bellavite, P., Ferraresi, A., Isidoro, C., 2023. Immune response and molecular mechanisms of cardiovascular adverse effects of spike proteins from SARS-CoV-2 and mRNA vaccines. *Biomedicines.* 11, 451.

Beretich, T., 2014. Patent Protection v. Tortious Liability - Confronting the legal liability for tortious behavior with intellectual property protection under patent laws: society's legal tradeoff with GMO-based patent rights and the damage the underlying technology and commercial behavior creates. SSRN. 1-31. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.2878912.

Bhagat, S., Yadav, N., Shah, J., et al., 2020. Novel corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic: current status and possible strategies for detection and treatment of the disease. *Expert Rev. Anti Infect. Ther.* 20, 1275-98.

Bhattacharjee, B., Lu, P., Monteiro, V.S., et al., 2025. Immunological and antigenic signatures associated with chronic illnesses after COVID-19 vaccination. medRxiv. 2025-02.

Brogna, C., Cristoni, S., Marino, G., et al., 2023. Detection of recombinant spike protein in the blood of individuals vaccinated against SARS-CoV-2: Possible molecular mechanisms. *Proteomics Clin. Appl.* 17, e2300048.

Buckhaults, P., 2023. Presentation to South Carolina Senate Medical Affairs Committee. Available at: <https://www.scstatehouse.gov/CommitteeInfo/SenateMedicalAffairsCommittee/PandemicPreparedness/Phillip-Buckhaults-SC-Senate-09122023-final.pdf>. Accessed April 03, 2025.

Buschmann, M.D., Carrasco, M.J., Alishetty, S., et al., 2021. Nanomaterial delivery systems for mRNA vaccines. *Vaccines*. 9, 65.

Cacciabauda, F., Altomare, R., Gioviale, M., et al., 2014. Genetically modified organism: definition and finality. *Prog. Nutr.* 15, 213-20.

Campbell, L., Blanchette, C., Small, E., 2019. Risk analysis of gene flow from cultivated, addictive, socialdrug plants to wild relatives. *Botanical Rev.* 85, 149-84.

Catanzaro, J.A., Hulscher, N., McCullough, P.A., 2025. Genomic integration and molecular dysregulation in aggressive stage IV bladder cancer following COVID-19 mRNA vaccination. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17122912. <https://zenodo.org/records/17122912>.

Cao, X., Xie, H., Song, M., et al., 2023. Cut-dip-budding delivery system enables genetic modifications in plants without tissue culture. *Innovation*. 4, 100345.

Carbone, M., Gazdar, A., Butel, J., 2020. SV40 and human mesothelioma. *Transl. Lung Cancer Res.* 9, S47-S59.

Castruita, J.A.S., Schneider, U.V., Mollerup, S., et al., 2023. SARS-CoV-2 spike mRNA vaccine sequences circulate in blood up to 28days after COVID-19 vaccination. *APMIS*. 131, 128-32.

Caulfield, T., Gold, R., Cho, M., 2000. Patenting human genetic material: refocusing the debate. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 1, 227-31.

Chatterjee, M., 2013. Law on Pharmaceutical Patents. SSRN. 1, 1-37.

Chaudhary, N., Newby, A.N., Arral, M.L., et al., 2024. Lipid nanoparticle structure and delivery route during pregnancy dictate mRNA potency, immunogenicity, and maternal and fetal outcomes. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U S A*, 121(11), e2307810121.

Cheong, J.G., Ravishankar, A., Sharma, S., et al., 2023. Epigenetic memory of coronavirus infection in innate immune cells and their progenitors. *Cell*. 186, 3882-902.

Chen, J.C., Hsu, M.H., Kuo, R.L., et al., 2025. mRNA-1273 is placenta-permeable and immunogenic in the fetus. *Mol. Ther. Nucleic Acids*. 36, 102489.

Coelho, A.C., García Díez, J., 2015. Biological risks and laboratory-acquired infections: a reality that cannot be ignored in health biotechnology. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 3, 56.

Cognetti J.S., Miller B.L., 2021. Monitoring serum spike protein with disposable photonic biosensors following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Sensors*. 21, 5827.

Comirnaty, 2021. Assessment report COVID-19 vaccine comirnaty. EMA/707383/2020 Corr1. 31:1-140. Available at: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/assessment-report/comirnaty-epar-public-assessment-report_en.pdf.

Corbett, K., Edwards, D., Leist, S., et al., 2020. SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine design enabled by prototype pathogen preparedness. *Nature*. 586, 567-71.

Cosentino, M., Marino, F., 2022. Understanding the pharmacology of COVID-19 mRNA vaccines: playing dice with the spike? *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 23, 10881.

Crespi, R., 2000. An analysis of moral issues affecting patenting inventions in the life sciences: A European perspective. *Sci. Eng. Ethics*. 6, 157-80.

De Beuckelaer, A., Pollard, C., Van Lint, S., et al., 2016. Type I interferons interfere with the capacity of mRNA lipoplex vaccines to elicit cytolytic T cell responses. *Mol. Ther.* 24, 2012-20.

Dederer, H.G., 2024. Gentechnikrecht und Patentrecht bei Pflanzen (No. 6-2024). *Studien zum deutschen Innovationssystem. Expertenkommission Forschung und Innovation (EFI)*. 6, 1-21.

Del Val, I.J., Kontoravdi, C., Nagy, J.M., 2010. Towards the implementation of quality by design to the production of therapeutic monoclonal antibodies with desired glycosylation patterns. *Biotechnol. Prog.* 26, 1505-27.

Di, J., Du, Z., Wu, K., et al., 2022. Biodistribution and non-linear gene expression of mRNA LNPs affected by delivery route and particle size. *Pharm. Res.* 39, 105-14.

Directive 98/44/EC, 1998. European Parliament, European Council; 6 July 1998; on the legal protection of biotechnological inventions (OJ L 213, 30.07.1998, 13).

Dolgin, E., 2021. The tangled history of mRNA vaccines. *Nature.* 597, 318-24.

Domazet-Lošo, T., 2022. mRNA vaccines: why is the biology of retroposition ignored? *Genes.* 13, 719.

Dresser, R., 1988. Ethical and legal issues in patenting new animal life. *Jurimetrics.* 28, 399-435.

EFSA - European Food Safety Authority, 2025. https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/glossary/gmo?utm_source. Accessed September 20, 2025.

EMA - European Medicines Agency, 2021. https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/assessment-report/comirnaty-epar-public-assessment-report_en.pdf. Accessed March 21, 2025.

European Union Directive 2001/18/EC. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/DE/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX%3A02003R1829-20210327&utm_source. Accessed Mai 07, 2025.

Evanega, S., Conrow, J., Adams, J., et al., 2022. The state of the 'GMO' debate-toward an increasingly favorable and less polarized media conversation on ag-biotech? *GM Crops Food.* 13, 38-49.

Faltus, T., 2023. The applicability of the European GMO legislation to epigenetically modified organisms. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 11, 1124131.

Federal Ministry of Justice, 2025. https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/patg/_1a.html, Accessed March 17, 2025.

Fernández Albújar, G., van der Meulen, B., 2017. The legal GMO concepts. Reassessment of the GMO definition in the light of new breeding techniques (NBTs). *European Institute for Food Law Working Paper Series.* 3.

Fertig, T.E., Chitoiu, L., Marta, D.S., et al., 2020. Vaccine mRNA can be detected in blood at 15 days post-vaccination. *Biomedicines.* 10, 1538.

Gao, K., Han, H., Cranick, M.G., et al., 2024. Widespread gene editing in the brain via in utero delivery of mRNA using acid-degradable lipid nanoparticles. *ACS Nano.* 18, 30293-306.

Garcia, R.E., 2001. Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs). European Parliament. Directorate-General for Research. Directorate A: Medium- and long-term Research. Division for Industry, Research, Energy, Environment and STOA. Briefing ENVI 504 EN. PE 309.707. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/note/join/2001/309707/DG-4-ENVI_NT\(2001\)309707_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/note/join/2001/309707/DG-4-ENVI_NT(2001)309707_EN.pdf); Accessed March 7, 2025.

Godt, C., 2018. Technology, patents and markets: the implied lessons of the EU commission's intervention in the broccoli/tomatoes case of 2016 for modern (plant) genome editing. *IIC-Int. Rev. Intell. Prop. Compet. Law.* 49, 512-35.

Gómez-Aguado, I., Rodríguez-Castejón, J., Vicente-Pascual, M., et al., 2020. Nucleic acid delivery by solid lipid nanoparticles containing switchable lipids. *Plasmid DNA vs messenger RNA.* *Molecules.* 25, 5995.

Grandi, N., Tramontano, E., Berkhout, B. 2021. Integration of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in infected human cells by retrotransposons: an unlikely hypothesis and old viral relationships. *Retrovirology,* 18(1), 34.

Halford, N.G., 2019. Legislation governing genetically modified and genome-edited crops in Europe: the need for change. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 99(1), 8-12.

Hancks, D., Kazazian, H., 2012. Active human retrotransposons: variation and disease. *Curr. Opin. Genet. Dev.* 22, 191-203.

Harui, A., Suzuki, S., Kochanek, S., et al., 1999. Frequency and stability of chromosomal integration of adenovirus vectors. *J. Virol.* 73, 6141-6.

Heinz, F.X., Stiasny, K., 2021. Distinguishing features of current COVID-19 vaccines: knowns and unknowns of antigen presentation and modes of action. *NPJ Vaccines.* 6, 104.

Hickey, K.J., Ward, E.H., 2024. The role of patents and regulatory exclusivities in drug pricing. *CRS.* 6, 1-61. R46679.

Hong, P., Waldenberger, M., Pritsch, M., et al., 2025. Differential DNA methylation 7 months after SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Clin. Epigenetics.* 17(1), 60.

- Horie, M., Honda, T., Suzuki, Y., et al., 2010. Endogenous non-retroviral RNA virus elements in mammalian genomes. *Nature*. 463, 84-7.
- Hou, X., Zaks, T., Langer, R., et al., 2021. Lipid nanoparticles for mRNA delivery. *Nat. Rev. Mater.* 6, 1078-94.
- Hussein, I., Chams, N., Chams, S., et al., 2015. Vaccines through centuries: major cornerstones of global health. *Front. Public Health*. 3, 269.
- Igyártó, B.Z., Qin, Z., 2024. The mRNA-LNP vaccines—the good, the bad and the ugly? *Front. Immunol.* 15, 1336906.
- Iwasaka, R., 2000. From Chakrabarty to chimeras: the growing need for evolutionary biology in patent law. *Yale Law J.* 109, 1505-34.
- Jackson, C., Farzan, M., Chen, B., et al., 2021. Mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 entry into cells. *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.* 23, 3-20.
- Jiang, L., 2020. Commercialization of the gene-edited crop and morality: challenges from the liberal patent law and the strict GMO law in the EU. *New Genet. Soc.* 39, 191-218.
- Jinek, M., Chylinski, K., Fonfara, I., et al., 2012. A programmable dual-RNA-guided DNA endonuclease in adaptive bacterial immunity. *Science*, 337(6096), 816-21.
- Kambic, R., 1988. Hindering the Progress of Science: The use of the patent system to regulate research on genetically altered animals. *Fordham Urban Law J.* 16, 441.
- Kämmerer, U., Schulz, V., Steger, K., 2024. BioNtech RNA-based COVID-19 injections contain large amounts of residual DNA including an SV40 promoter/enhancer sequence. *Sci. Public Health Policy Law.* 5, 2019-24.
- Karikó, K., Buckstein, M., Ni, H., et al., 2005. Suppression of RNA recognition by Toll-like receptors: the impact of nucleoside modification and the evolutionary origin of RNA. *Immunity*. 23, 165-75.
- Karikó, K., Muramatsu, H., Welsh, F. A., 2008. Incorporation of pseudouridine into mRNA yields superior nonimmunogenic vector with increased translational capacity and biological stability. *Mol. Ther.* 16, 1833-40.
- Karikó, K., Muramatsu, H., Ludwig, J., et al., 2011. Generating the optimal mRNA for therapy: HPLC purification eliminates immune activation and improves translation of nucleoside-modified, protein-encoding mRNA. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 39, e142.
- Katzmarski, N., Domínguez-Andrés, J., Cirovic, B., et al., 2021. Transmission of trained immunity and heterologous resistance to infections across generations. *Nat. Immunol.* 22, 1382-90.
- Khachigian, L.M., 2020. Pharmaceutical patents: reconciling the human right to health with the incentive to invent. *Drug Discov. Today*. 25, 1135-41.
- Khan, S., Ullah, M.W., Siddique, R., et al., 2016. Role of recombinant DNA technology to improve life. *Int. J. Genomics*. 2016, 2405954.
- Kim, E., Jeon, M., Kim, K., et al., 2021. Spike proteins of SARS-CoV-2 induce pathological changes in molecular delivery and metabolic function in the brain endothelial cells. *Viruses*. 13, 2021.
- Kim, S.C., Sekhon, S.S., Shin, W.-R., et al., 2022. Modifications of mRNA vaccine structural elements for improving mRNA stability and translation efficiency. *Mol. Cell Toxicol.* 18, 1-8.
- Klenerman, P., Hengartner, H., Zinkernagel, R.M., 1997. A non-retroviral RNA virus persists in DNA form. *Nature*. 390, 298–301.
- Kolevatykh, M.A., 2024. mRNA vaccines: reasonable concerns about the consequences using the example of Covid-19 vaccines. *Medicina*. 12, 69-84.
- König, B., Kirchner, J.O., 2024. Methodological considerations regarding the quantification of DNA impurities in the covid-19 mRNA vaccine comirnaty®. *Methods Protoc.* 7, 41.
- Krauson, A.J., Casimero, F.V.C., Siddique, Z., et al., 2023. Duration of SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine persistence and factors associated with cardiac involvement in recently vaccinated patients. *NPJ Vaccines*. 8, 141.
- Kyriakopoulos, A.M., McCullough, P.A., 2021. Synthetic mRNAs; their analogue caps and contribution to disease. *Diseases*. 9, 57.
- Laforest, L.C., Nadakuduti, S.S., 2022. Advances in delivery mechanisms of CRISPR gene-editing reagents in plants. *Front. Genome Ed.* 4, 830178.
- Lamont, J., Lacey, J., 2020. Genetically Modified Organisms. *International Encyclopedia of Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444367072.WBIEE101>.
- Landrum, A.R., Hallman, W.K., Jamieson, K.H., 2019. Examining the impact of expert voices: communicating the scientific consensus on genetically-modified organisms. *Environ. Commun.* 13, 51-70.

- Li C, Lee A, Grigoryan L, et al., 2022a. Mechanisms of innate and adaptive immunity to the PfizerBioNTech BNT162b2 vaccine. *Nat. Immunol.* 23, 543-55.
- Li, M., Yang, Z., Chang, C., 2022b. Susceptibility is new resistance: wheat susceptibility genes and exploitation in resistance breeding. *Agriculture.* 12, 1419.
- Li, X., Chang, J., Chen, S.M., et al., 2021. Genomic feature analysis of betacoronavirus provides insights into SARS and COVID-19 pandemics. *Front. Microbiol.* 12, 614494.
- Liu, M., La Croix, S., 2015. A cross-country index of intellectual property rights in pharmaceutical inventions. *Res. Policy.* 44, 206-16.
- Malone, R.W., Felgner, P.L., Verma, I.M., 1989. Cationic liposome-mediated RNA transfection. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U S A.* 1989, 86, 6077-81.
- Manzanares-Palenzuela, C., Martín-Fernández, B., López, M., et al., 2014. Electrochemical genosensors as innovative tools for detection of genetically modified organisms. *Trends Anal. Chem.* 66, 19-31.
- Mariappan, K., Zhou, D., 2019. A threat of farmers' suicide and the opportunity in organic farming for sustainable agricultural development in India. *Sustainability.* 11, 2400.
- Maruggi, G., Zhang, C., Li, J., et al., 2019. mRNA as a transformative technology for vaccine development to control infectious diseases. *Mol. Ther.* 27, 757-72.
- McCann, N., O'Connor, D., Lambe, T., et al., 2022. Viral vector vaccines. *Curr. Opin. Immunol.* 77, 102210.
- McKernan, K., Kyriakopoulos, A.M., McCullough, P.A., 2021. Differences in vaccine and SARS-CoV-2 replication derived mRNA: implications for cell biology and future disease. *OSF Preprints.* DOI: 10.31219/osf.io/bcsa6.
- McKernan, K., 2023. 182nd meeting of the Vaccines and Related Biological Products Advisory Committee (VRBPAC). Food and Drug Administration (FDA), Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research (CBER). Video Conference. June 15, 2023. Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/media/169804/download>. Accessed April 03, 2025.
- McKernan, K., Helbert, Y., Kane, L.T., et al., 2023. Sequencing of bivalent Moderna and Pfizer mRNA vaccines reveals nanogram to microgram quantities of expression vector dsDNA per dose. *OSF Preprints.* DOI: 10.31219/osf.io/b9t7m.
- Merchant, H.A., 2022. Comment on Aldén et al. Intracellular reverse transcription of Pfizer BioNTech COVID-19 mRNA vaccine BNT162b2 in vitro in human liver cell line. *Curr. Issues Mol. Biol.* 44, 1115-26.
- Mistry, P., Barmania, F., Mellet, J., et al., 2022. SARS-CoV-2 variants, vaccines, and host immunity. *Front. Immunol.* 12, 809244.
- Moderna, 2020. Quarterly report pursuant to section 13 or 15(d) of the securities exchange act of 1934. For the quarterly period ended June 30, Aug. 6 2020. Accessed July 22, 2021, at <https://www.sec.gov/Archives/edgar/data/1682852/000168285220000017/mrna-20200630.htm>.
- Moderna, 2021. Assessment report COVID-19 Vaccine Moderna Common. EMA/15689/2021 Corr1*1. 31:1-169. Available at: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/assessment-report/spikevax-previously-covid-19-vaccine-moderna-eparpublic-assessment-report_en.pdf.
- Morais, P., Adachi, H., Yu, Y.T., 2021. The critical contribution of pseudouridine to mRNA COVID-19 vaccines. *Front. Cell Dev. Biol.* 9, 789427.
- Mulligan, M., Lyke, K., Kitchin, N., et al., 2020. Phase I/II study of COVID-19 RNA vaccine BNT162b1 in adults. *Nature.* 586, 589-93.
- Mulrone, T.E., Pöyry, T., Yam-Puc, J.C., et al., 2024. N1-methylpseudouridylation of mRNA causes +1 ribosomal frameshifting. *Nature.* 625, 189-94.
- Murphy, D.B., 1998. Guidance for industry: FDA guidance for human somatic cell therapy and gene therapy. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research, Food and Drug Administration, Accessed March 17, 2025, Available online: <https://www.fda.gov/media/72402/download>.
- Nance, K.D., Meier J.L., 2021. Modifications in an emergency: the role of N1-methylpseudouridine in COVID-19 vaccines. *ACS Cent Sci.* 7, 748-56.
- Nawaz, M.A., Golokhvast, K.S., Tsatsakis, A.M., et al., 2020. GMOs, biodiversity and ecosystem processes. *GMOs: Implications for Biodiversity Conservation and Ecological Processes.* 3-17.
- Ndeupen, S., Qin, Z., Jacobsen, S., et al., 2021. The mRNA-LNP platform's lipid nanoparticle component used in preclinical vaccine studies is highly inflammatory. *iScience.* 24, 103479.

- Neira-Monsalve, E., Serrato, M.L., Ospina, C.A., 2023. Cisgenic crops: biodiversity, ecosystems, and environment. *Cisgenic Crops: Safety, Legal and Social Issues*. 1-29.
- Nicol, D., Dreyfuss, R., Gold, E., et al., 2019. International divergence in gene patenting. *Annu. Rev. Genomics Hum. Genet.* 20, 519-41.
- O'Connor, K., 1993. Patents for genetically modified animals. *J. Anim. Sci.* 71, 34-40.
- Ogata, A.F., Cheng, C.A., Desjardins, M., et al., 2022. Circulating SARS-CoV-2 vaccine antigen detected in the plasma of mRNA-1273 vaccine recipients. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* 74, 715-8.
- Oliver, S., Gargano, J., Marin, M., et al., 2020. The advisory committee on immunization practices' interim recommendation for use of Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine - United States, December 2020. *MMWR.* 69, 1922-4.
- Oliver, S., Gargano, J., Marin, M., et al., 2021. The advisory committee on immunization practices' interim recommendation for use of Moderna COVID-19 vaccine - United States, December 2020. *MMWR.* 69, 1653-6.
- Orlandini von Niessen, A.G., Poleganov, M.A., Rechner, C., et al., 2019. Improving mRNA-based therapeutic gene delivery by expression-augmenting 3' UTRs identified by cellular library screening. *Mol. Ther.* 27, 824-36.
- Pardi, N., Tuyishime, S., Muramatsu, H., et al., 2015. Expression kinetics of nucleoside-modified mRNA delivered in lipid nanoparticles to mice by various routes. *J. Control Release.* 217, 345-51.
- Pardi, N., Hogan, M.J., Porter, F.W., et al., 2018. mRNA vaccines—A new era in vaccinology. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 17, 261-79.
- Park, J., Lagniton, P., Liu, Y., et al., 2021. mRNA vaccines for COVID-19: what, why and how. *Int. J. Biol. Sci.* 17, 1446-60.
- Parr, C.J., Wada, S., Kotake, K., et al., 2020. N1-Methylpseudouridine substitution enhances the performance of synthetic mRNA switches in cells. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 48, e35.
- Parry, P.I., Lefringhausen, A., Turni, C., et al., 2023. 'Spikeopathy': COVID-19 spike protein is pathogenic, from both virus and vaccine mRNA. *Biomedicines.* 11, 2287.
- Parry, R., Gifford, R.J., Lytras, S., et al., 2021. No evidence of SARS-CoV-2 reverse transcription and integration as the origin of chimeric transcripts in patient tissues. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 118(33), e2109066118.
- Pekova, S., 2025. Quantitative Multiplex Real-Time PCR analysis of Moderna (Spikevax) and Pfizer (BNT162b2) vaccines. TILIA LABORATORIES s.r.o., Pchery, Czech Republic. 08.03.2025. Available at: <https://www.10letters.org/CzechResearch.pdf>. Accessed April 03, 2025.
- Plotkin, S.A., 2003. Vaccines, vaccination, and vaccinology. *J. Infect. Dis.* 187, 1349-59.
- Plotkin, S.A., 2014. History of vaccination. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U S A.* 111, 12283-7.
- Polykretis, P., McCullough, P.A., 2022. Rational harm-benefit assessments by age group are required for continued COVID-19 vaccination. *Scand. J. Immunol.* 98, e13242.
- Posa, A., 2025. Spike protein-related proteinopathies: A focus on the neurological side of spikeopathies. *Ann. Anat.* 152662.
- Poulin, D.L., DeCaprio, J.A., 2006. Is there a role for SV40 in human cancer? *J. Clin. Oncol.* 24, 4356-65.
- Prahl, M., Golan, Y., Cassidy, A. G., et al., 2022. Evaluation of transplacental transfer of mRNA vaccine products and functional antibodies during pregnancy and infancy. *Nat. Commun.* 13(1), 4422.
- Qian, Y., 2007. Do national patent laws stimulate domestic innovation in a global patenting environment? A cross-country analysis of pharmaceutical patent protection, 1978–2002. *Rev. Econ. Stat.* 89, 436-53.
- Qin, Z., Bouteau, A., Herbst, C., et al., 2022. Pre-exposure to mRNA-LNP inhibits adaptive immune responses and alters innate immune fitness in an inheritable fashion. *PLoS Pathogens.* 18, e1010830.
- Raoult, D., 2024. Confirmation of the presence of vaccine DNA in the Pfizer anti-COVID-19 vaccine. *HAL.* hal-04778576.
- Rasheed, M., Awais, M., Khalid, M., et al., 2022. The role of genetically-modified (GM) crops in food security. *Life Sci. J.* 19, 26-30.
- Rehman, M., Fariha, C., Anwar, A., et al., 2020. Novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic: A recent mini review. *Comput. Struct. Biotechnol. J.* 19, 612-23.
- Rijkers, G., Weterings, N., Obregón-Henao, A., et al., 2021. Antigen presentation of mRNA-based and virus-vectored SARS-CoV-2 vaccines. *Vaccines.* 9, 848.
- Röltgen, K., Nielsen, S.C.A., Silva, O., 2022. Immune imprinting, breadth of variant recognition and germinal center response in human SARS-CoV-2 infection and vaccination. *Cell.* 185, 1025-40.

Roorda, J., 2017. Patents, hidden novelty, and food safety. *Florida Law Rev.* 68, 657.

Rotondo, J., Mazzoni, E., Bononi, I., et al., 2019. Association between simian virus 40 and human tumors. *Front. Oncol.* 9, 670.

Sahin, U., Kariko, K., Tureci, O., 2014. mRNA-based therapeutics-developing a new class of drugs. *Nat. Rev. Drug. Discov.* 13, 759-80.

Santos, A., Sauer, M., Neil, A. J., et al., 2022. Absence of SARS-CoV-2 Spike glycoprotein expression in placentas from individuals after mRNA SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. *Mod. Pathol.* 35(9), 1175-80.

Sattar, S., Kabat, J., Jerome, K., et al., 2023. Nuclear translocation of spike mRNA and protein is a novel feature of SARS-CoV-2. *Front. Microbiol.* 14, 1073789.

Schlake, T., Thess, A., Fotin-Mleczek, M., et al., 2012. Developing mRNA-vaccine technologies. *RNA Biol.* 9, 1319-30.

Schmeling, M., Manniche, V., Hansen, P.R., 2023. Batch-dependent safety of the BNT162b2 mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. *Eur. J. Clin. Invest.*, 53, e13998.

Seltzer, R., 1988. Resolution sought on animal patent dispute. *Chem. Eng. News.* 66, 5-6.

Sern, A.M., Markel, H., 2005. The history of vaccines and immunization: familiar patterns, new challenges. *Health Aff. (Millwood).* 24, 611-21.

Shadlen, K.C., Sampat, B.N., Kapczynski, A., 2020. Patents, trade and medicines: past, present and future. *Rev. Int. Polit. Econ.* 27, 75-97.

Sharova, L., Sharov, A., Nedorezov, T., et al., 2008. Database for mRNA Half-Life of 19 977 Genes Obtained by DNA Microarray Analysis of Pluripotent and Differentiating Mouse Embryonic Stem Cells. *DNA Res.* 16, 45-58.

Sherkow, J., Greely, H., 2015. The history of patenting genetic material. *Annu. Rev. Genet.* 49,161-82.

Simonis, A., Theobald, S.J., Koch, A.E., et al., 2025. Persistent epigenetic memory of SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccination in monocyte-derived macrophages. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* 21, 341-60.

Singh, R.B., Mishra, S., Saxena, P., et al., 2022. Genetically modified organisms and foods: perspectives and challenges. *Funct. Foods Nutraceuticals Metabol. Non-Commun. Dis.* 34, 493-505.

Smith, P., Kong, X., 2022. Intellectual property rights and trade: The exceptional case of GMOs. *World Econ.* 45, 763-811.

Smits, N., Rasmussen, J., Bodea, G.O., et al., 2021. No evidence of human genome integration of SARS-CoV-2 found by long-read DNA sequencing. *Cell Rep.* 36, 109530.

Speicher, D.J., Rose, J., Gutsch, L.M., et al., 2023. DNA fragments detected in monovalent and bivalent Pfizer/BioNTech and Moderna modRNA COVID-19 vaccines from Ontario, Canada: Exploratory dose response relationship with serious adverse events. DOI: 10.31219/osf.io/mjc97. Available at: https://osf.io/preprints/osf/mjc97_v1.

Speicher, D.J., Rose, J., McKernan, K., 2025. Quantification of residual plasmid DNA and SV40 promoter-enhancer sequences in Pfizer/BioNTech and Moderna modRNA COVID-19 vaccines from Ontario, Canada. *Autoimmunity.* 58, 2551517.

Srivastava, I.K., Liu, M.A., 2003. Gene vaccines. *Ann. Intern. Med.* 138, 550-9.

Straus, J., 2000. Genpatentierung - Eine „abstruse Idee“? *Dtsch. Ärztebl.* 97, 1061-4.

Swingle, K.L., Safford, H.C., Geisler, H.C., et al., 2023. Ionizable lipid nanoparticles for in vivo mRNA delivery to the placenta during pregnancy. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 145, 4691-706.

Tang, X., Wu, C., Li, X., et al., 2020. On the origin and continuing evolution of SARS-CoV-2. *Nat. Sci. Rev.* 7, 1012-23.

Theobald, S.J., Simonis, A., Georgomanolis, T., et al., 2021. Long-lived macrophage reprogramming drives spike protein-mediated inflammasome activation in COVID-19. *EMBO Mol. Med.* 13, e14150.

Theoharides, T.C., Kempuraj, D., 2023. Role of SARS-CoV-2 spike-protein-induced activation of microglia and mast cells in the pathogenesis of neuro-COVID. *Cells.* 12, 688.

Trkulja, V., Ballina, D., Vidović, S., et al., 2018. Genetically Modified Organisms—present situation and future prospects. *Food Safety Agency Bosnia Herzegovina.* 1, 1-124.

Trougakos, I.P., Terpos, E., Alexopoulos, H., et al., 2022. Adverse effects of COVID-19 mRNA vaccines: the spike hypothesis. *Trends. Mol. Med.* 28, 542-54.

Turni, C., Lefringhausen, A., 2022. Covid-19 vaccines - An Australian Review. *J. Clin. Exp. Immunol.* 7, 491-508.

- von Ranke, N., Zhang, W., Anokin, P., et al., 2025. Synthetic mRNA Vaccines and Transcriptomic Dysregulation: Evidence from New-Onset Adverse Events and Cancers Post-Vaccination. DOI: 10.20944/preprints202507.2155.v1. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/394007467_Synthetic_m-RNA_Vaccines_and_Transcriptomic_Dysregulation_Evidence_from_New-Onset_Averse_Events_and_Cancers_Post-Vaccination.
- Walsh, E.E., Frenck, R.W., Jr., Falsey, A.R., et al., 2020. Safety and immunogenicity of two RNA-based COVID-19 vaccine candidates. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 383, 2439-50.
- Wang, M., Valadez-Ingersoll, M., Gilmore, T. D. 2024a. Control of nuclear localization of the nucleocapsid protein of SARS-CoV-2. *Virology*, 600, 110232.
- Wang, R., Lee, J.H., Kim, J., et al., 2023. SARS-CoV-2 restructures host chromatin architecture. *Nat. Microbiol.* 8(4), 679-94.
- Wang, T.J., Kim, A., Kim, K., 2024b. A rapid detection method of replication-competent plasmid DNA from COVID-19 mRNA vaccines for quality control. *J. High School Sci.* 8, 427-39.
- WHO - World Health Organization, 2025. https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/food-genetically-modified/?utm_source=chatgpt.com. Accessed September 20, 2025.
- Wick, P., Malek, A., Manser, P., et al., 2010. Barrier capacity of human placenta for nanosized materials. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 118, 432-6.
- Wilson, J., 2007. GM Crops: patently wrong? *J. Agric. Environ. Ethics.* 20, 261-83.
- Xu, W., Brynjolfsson, S., Fu, W., 2022. Use of genetically modified algae: consumption safety challenges, current legislations, and socio-economic and environmental concerns. *Microalgae Sustain. Prod.* 9, 178-90.
- Yali, W., 2022. Application of Genetically Modified Organism (GMO) crop technology and its implications in modern agriculture. *Int. J. Appl. Agric. Sci.* 8, 14-20.
- Yamamoto, T., Koyama, H., Kurajoh, M., et al., 2011. Biochemistry of uridine in plasma. *Clinica Chimica Acta.* 412, 1712-24.
- Yang, E., van Nimwegen, E., Zavolan, M., et al., 2003. Decay rates of human mRNAs: correlation with functional characteristics and sequence attributes. *Genome Res.* 13, 1863-72.
- Yin, Y., Liu, X.Z., He, X., et al., 2021. Exogenous coronavirus interacts with endogenous retrotransposon in human cells. *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.* 11, 609160.
- Yonker, L.M., Swank, Z., Bartsch, Y.C., et al., 2023. Circulating spike protein detected in post-COVID-19 mRNA vaccine myocarditis. *Circulation.* 147, 867-76.
- Zhang, J., Cruz-Cosme, R., Zhuang, M.W., et al., 2020. A systemic and molecular study of subcellular localization of SARS-CoV-2 proteins. *Signal Transduct. Target. Ther.* 5, 269.
- Zhang, L., Richards, A., Barrasa, M.I., et al., 2021. Reverse-transcribed SARS-CoV-2 RNA can integrate into the genome of cultured human cells and can be expressed in patient-derived tissues. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U S A.* 118, e2105968118.
- Zhang, L., Bisht, P., Flamier, A., et al., 2023. LINE1-mediated reverse transcription and genomic integration of SARS-CoV-2 mRNA detected in virus-infected but not in viral mRNA-transfected cells. *Viruses.* 15, 629.
- Zheng, C., Baum, B.J., Iadarola, M.J., et al., 2000. Genomic integration and gene expression by a modified adenoviral vector. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 18, 176-80.
- Zhong, C., Cohen, K., Lin, X., et al., 2024. COVID-19 vaccine mRNA biodistribution: maternal and fetal exposure risks. *Am. J. Reprod. Immunol.* 92, e13934.
- Zhou, Y., Peng, Z., Seven, E.S., et al., 2018. Crossing the blood-brain barrier with nanoparticles. *J. Control Release.* 270, 290-303.
- Zhu, M., Lu, X., Wang, D., et al., 2025. A narrative review of epigenetic marker in H3K27ac and its emerging potential as a therapeutic target in cancer. *Epigenomics.* 17, 263-79.
- Zietsman, M.S., Shanahan, M.A., Barrozo, E.R., et al., 2024. 817 Trans-placental transport of a novel fluorescent lipid nanoparticle in a pre-clinical fetal therapy murine model. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* 230(1), S434-S435.
- Zimny, T., 2015. Recent changes to EU law on GMOs and their potential influence on the patentability of GM plants. Some remarks on possible side effects of Directive 2015/412/EU. *Biotechnologia. J. Biotechnol. Comput. Biol. Bionanotechnol.* 96, 161-70.